

QUANTITATIVE SEPARATION OF CALCIUM FROM STRONTIUM USING ACETONE AS A SOLVENT.

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A quantitative separation of calcium from strontium has been effected by using acetone as a solvent. The method is based upon the principle that calcium nitrate is highly soluble in acetone while strontium nitrate is insoluble in the same solvent.

Data on the separation of calcium from strontium in analysis appear to be meagre. One method is to separate the nitrates by a mixture of ether and anhydrous absolute alcohol (1 : 1) ; alternatively, anhydrous amyl alcohol is used (Scott, "Standard Methods of Quantitative Analysis", 1937, Vol I, p. 6). Tananaev reports (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1935, 100, 391) the use of glacial acetic acid for their separation as dry nitrates. Further quantitative results confirming this claim are, however, lacking.

With a view to selecting a solvent which is easily accessible in the purest condition, we carried out a series of investigations with various organic solvents and we have found that acetone serves the above purpose quite satisfactorily.

Strontium nitrate is insoluble in acetone while calcium nitrate is highly soluble. It follows, therefore, that the two elements should be present in the mixture as dry nitrates. If they are not initially present as nitrates, they have to be converted into dry nitrates by the usual method (*cf.* Scott, *loc. cit.*).

EXPERIMENTAL.

The order of solubility of strontium nitrate in acetone as found by us at 35° is 1 part in 15,000 parts of acetone. Calcium nitrate is highly soluble.

Various mixtures of calcium nitrate and strontium nitrate were prepared in water solution and the results of analysis according to this procedure have been recorded in the accompanying table.

A known quantity of strontium nitrate solution (about 5%) was taken in a weighing bottle and evaporated to dryness, the weight of the residue corresponding to the amount of strontium nitrate taken. To this residue of strontium nitrate again a known quantity of calcium nitrate solution (about 5%) was added and evaporated to dryness at 170°. The weight

of this residue less the weight of strontium nitrate taken gives the weight of calcium nitrate taken.

The mixture of the dry nitrates was prepared by evaporation and dried at 170° . Calcium nitrate was extracted with acetone from strontium nitrate and the filtration was done through a sintered glass crucible. The acetone solution was evaporated to dryness and the residual calcium nitrate was further dried at 170° and weighed as such. The strontium nitrate left behind after extraction in the sintered glass crucible was dried and weighed.

TABLE I.

Mixture No	Sr(NO ₃) ₂		Ca(NO ₃) ₂	
	Actual.	Found.	Actual.	Found.
I	0.1610	0.1594	0.1640	0.1670
II	0.1396	0.1360	0.3880	0.3840
III	0.3430	0.3464	0.1784	0.1740
IV	0.3240	0.3230	0.2550	0.2542
V	0.4820	0.4800	0.1800	0.1780
VI	0.4860	0.4854	0.3490	0.3480
VII	0.6116	0.6120	0.1750	0.1764
VIII	0.1600	0.1610	0.5060	0.5070
IX	0.3184	0.3180	0.5390	0.5400

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